

TECHNOLOGIES FOR INCREASING THE MILK PRODUCTIVITY OF CATTLE

Jangabaeva Ramash Qayirbergenovna

Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Biotechnology and Animal Husbandry University.

Trainee teacher

Madetova Nilufar Maxkamjon qizi

Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Biotechnology and Animal Husbandry University.

2nd year student of veterinary sanitary expertise

Abstract: *This article describes ways to increase milk productivity of cattle and methods of increasing cattle milk using milk production technology.*

Key words: *Cattle, fertility, dairy products, method, feed, raw materials, lactation, premixes with amino acids and probiotics*

INTRODUCTION

The milk yield of cattle is called the amount of milk obtained from one cow during a certain period of time: day, week, month. This is one of the main indicators of the economic efficiency of the economy in animal husbandry. The evaluation is done for each cow and for the whole herd as a whole. The index of milk productivity of cows depends on many factors and can change both up and down.

The higher the milk yield, the lower the feed costs per 1 kg of finished product. As a result, the price of milk will also decrease, since about 60% of the price is the cost of feeding cattle. Keeping high-yielding animals is on average 1.5-2 times cheaper than regular livestock, so producers are interested in increasing milk production.

Composition and properties of milk. Milk productivity is characterized by the quantity and quality of milk. Milk is a biological fluid produced by mammary glands. The complex chemical composition and properties of milk determine its importance as a food product for humans, as feed for newborn calves and as a raw material for making cheese, butter and other types of dairy products.

(table. 1). Milk content (%)

Indicator	Includes	Vibrations
Water	87,5	82,7- 90,7
Dry matter-total	12,5	9,3 - 17,3
Including: fat	3,8	2,7 - 7,0
Proteins	3,3	2,0 - 5,0
Casein	2,7	2,2 - 4,5
Albumin	0,5	0,2 - 0,6
globulin	0,1	0,05 - 0,15
milk sugar (lactose)	4,7	4,0 - 5,3
mineral matter (ash)	0,7	0,5 - 1,0

Milk contains more than 100 components: fats, proteins, carbohydrates, minerals, enzymes, hormones and other substances. All of them are easily and almost completely absorbed by the body: fat - 95%, proteins - 96%, carbohydrates - 98%. Milk fat, proteins, sugars and minerals make up its dry matter and determine the nutritional value of milk.

METHOD AND RESULTS:

Evaluation of milk productivity is necessary in breeding and commodity herds. This assessment information is important for selecting cows and determining the genetic characteristics of bulls, recording animals in stud books, organizing proper feeding of animals, as well as working on dairy farms, etc.

A cow's mammary glands do not work constantly, but during a certain period of time called lactation, which is closely related to the function of reproduction.

During the calendar year, the cow should not be Yalova, should calve to start and finish lactation. Lactation, the period from calving to initiation when cows stop milking before the next calving, can be shorter or longer than 305 days. It mainly depends on the duration of the service period and partly on the duration of the dry

period. The calculation of individual milk yield, regardless of its duration, is carried out during the entire lactation period, and for comparison, they receive data for the first 305 days of lactation or a shortened completed day.

The service period is the time from calving to insemination. Late insemination of cows results in a longer lactation period or a longer dry period. Both are undesirable, as this results in less milk being produced from cows.

Drought-resistant period - the time from initiation to calving. Its duration should be 60 days. But this can change depending on the condition, age and other factors of the cow.

Individual milking and fat and protein content of milk are recorded monthly during control days, for which control milking of cows is carried out.

The average percentage of fat (protein) in milk during lactation is calculated as follows: milk yield for each month of lactation is multiplied by the content of fat (protein) in that month (as a percentage). The obtained indicators (1% milk amount) for all months of lactation are summarized and divided by the milk yield for lactation.

The average milk yield of cows in a herd or other groups corresponds to 1 dairy cow or 1 fodder cow in the relevant period.

The base fat content of milk is 1% divided by the specified base fat content (3.4%). Amount of milk for 1 food. fed feed (payment for food with milk) or the number of feed units per 1 kg of milk (feed costs).

To convert to kilograms, if the amount of milk is considered in volume units (liters), it is multiplied by the density of milk.

In the breeding of specialized meat breeds, the milk yield of cows is evaluated by the live weight of the calf at weaning in 6-8 months. age
According to the level of milk productivity, all cattle breeds can be divided into three groups:

Table 2

Indicator	group I	group II	group III
The name of the breed	Red steppe, black and colorful.	Angliya, Jersi, Yaroslavl	Kostroma, Lebedinsky, Simmental
Sutning yog ' miqdori, %	3,6-3,7	4.3 dan	middle
Annual milk yield, tons	4-5	3-4	Different sizes

There are also breeds of cattle that differ in their anatomical characteristics and productivity. For example, dairy and dairy cows give milk of different composition.

A number of measures are being developed to increase the productivity of animals on farms.

The following will help to increase milk production:

- creating a varied and balanced diet, including cakes, wheat, water and roughage;
- providing sufficient water, on average 4-6 liters for every 1 liter of milk;
- introduction of nutritional supplements with vitamins, minerals, trace elements;
- use of probiotics that improve feed conversion and reduce the level of disease in the herd;
- compliance with the milking schedule;
- planning of calving seasons;
- competent milking technique using machines that give a quarter of the udder at once;
- udder hygiene and massage to prevent milk stagnation;
- increase the daylight hours to 16 hours, preferably due to natural light;
- outdoor feeding or ventilation of the farm;

- maintaining an optimal level of humidity and air temperature in the pen;
- health monitoring and proper treatment;
- treat the cow well without shouting, beating or aggression.
- Above we mentioned how the diet affects the milk production of cows. Ferment Group experts have developed a range of premixes with amino acids and probiotics to help increase milk production. The composition of additives takes into account the age of the cow, the life cycle stage, and the physiological needs of dairy animals. Adding premixes to the diet increases the nutritional value of the feed. Our supplements also make it easy to count ingredients, and help you accurately dose vitamins, macro and micronutrients. The assortment includes premixes for cows in the dry period, nets, transit and lactating animals.
- The increase in productivity in dairy farming depends on the compensation in the nutrition of all substances used for milk production, namely proteins and calcium, fats and phosphorus, carbohydrates. If minerals are not enough with food, the cow begins to use its internal reserves, which leads to rapid exhaustion.
- One of the first ways to increase milk production using milk production technology is to organize good nutrition. It should not only contain plenty of water, all the necessary vitamins, but also be varied and balanced. Good nutrition not only increases daily milk production, but also improves milk quality, its nutritional value and heat resistance. A good diet should consist of silage, preferably legumes or corn, hay and hay, root crops, cereals, vegetables, fruits and animal feed:
 - Meat meal,
 - Fish food,
 - Whey.

Em - be sure to add hay yeast and special premixes - Gold Felucen or Felucen.

How much milk a cow gives is affected by how much water she drinks. Dehydration causes a rapid decrease in lactation. It is better to set up raceways for cows to drink when needed. If this is not possible, water in buckets is offered every two to three hours, always before and after feeding, as well as after milking.

Increased productivity in dairy farming also depends on the basic requirements for start-up, a sufficiently long period of deadwood and proper establishment in the first hundred days after calving. Proper preparation procedures before milking help to increase daily milk yield. This is especially important for the first calf. Such procedures include forced udder massage - thanks to massage movements, the pituitary gland receives a signal to release the hormone oxytocin. When the hormone reaches the udder, it stimulates the contraction of the alveoli and therefore easier milk ejection. Usually, the nipples are ready to give milk after the first minute of massage. Oxytocin is in the blood for only five to six minutes, so you need to start milking immediately after the massage.

CONCLUSION:

The correct process of milking also affects the increase of milk in a cow. If the animal is milked by hand, it should be milked with a fist - this is correct and safe for the cow. If milking equipment is used, it must be ensured that the milking nipples do not pass into the udder and that the device is working properly, releasing all the udder.

Increasing productivity in dairy farming is also possible by increasing daylight hours. If the duration of daylight hours is more than 16 hours, milk production increases by 8-10% during the month. For this, large windows and additional bright lighting are installed in warehouses. In addition to long daylight hours, animals also need good exercise. Cows that are able to walk daily usually give more milk. Keeping animals in the pasture in the summer months has a good effect not only on the lactation period, but also on general health.

Milk production on dairy farms is often done with the help of food additives such as sel-Plex and I-Sac. These food additives affect both milk composition and milk composition equally. Two and a half and five grams should be given to each cow per day, respectively. Sel-Plex and I-Sac allow the full use of the genetic potential of cows in productivity. Disadvantages of this method: labor intensity, duration of use and lack of information on the effect of drugs on quality characteristics, which is very important for its use in a dairy factory.

LITERATURE

Алиев, А., & Мусаева, М. З. К. (2021). СИСТЕМЫ ЗАЩИТЫ БИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 393-396.

Aliyev, A. A. (2021). СИСТЕМЫ ЗАЩИТЫ БИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

Исмоилов Ш. М., Абдужалилов С., Алиев А. КЎНДАЛАНГ КЕСИМИ ИХТИЁРИЙ БЎЛГАН СТЕРЖЕНЛАРНИНГ ГЕОМЕТРИК ВА МЕХАНИК ПАРАМЕТРЛАРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ АЛГОРИТМИ //Results of National Scientific Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 49-56.

Ayubjon o'gli, A. A. (2022). MOLIVAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAQIDA TUSHUNCHASI VA UALARNING TURLARI. *Academic Research*, 1(4), 64-69.

Ayubjon o'gli A. A. PRINCIPLES OF FINANCIAL INNOVATION //Academic Research. – 2022. - Jild 1. – №. 4. - S. 70-73.

Ayubjon o'g'li A. A., Islomjon I. AXBORT TIZIMLARINING DASTURIY TAMINOTI BANK SOHASIDAGI AHAMIYATI //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS". – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 67-73.

Ibrohimjon o'g'li I. I., Ayubjon o'g'li A. A. LOYIXALARNI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA AXBOROT XAVFSIZLIGIDA

RISKLARNI TAHLILI //Results of national scientific research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 39-44.

Doshanova G. The Creative Evolution of Philosophical Thinking in the Quatrain of Poet S. Sayyid //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – C. 8996-9000.

Doshanova G. I. MAHMUD TOIR LIRIKASINING BADIY XUSUSIYATLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. - Jild 2. – №. 4. - P. 1041-1049.